

Man-Woman Relationship Depicted in Vijay Tendulkar's Plays, *Silence! The Court is in Session* and *Kamala*

Pradip Babaso Gaikwad

Assistant Professor of English

Mahavir Mahavidyalaya, Kolhapur

Corresponding Author – Pradip Babaso Gaikwad

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.19312027

Introduction:

Vijay Tendulkar is one of the most eminent modern Indian playwrights. He was born in 1928 in Kolhapur, Maharashtra. He has written thirty full length plays and twenty three one-act plays. He wrote plays for children, four collections of short stories, one novel and five volumes of literary essays and social criticism. Tendulkar's writing has contributed to a remarkable transformation of modern literary landscape of Maharashtra as well as India as a whole. He has translated many works. He wrote stories and screenplays for eight films in Marathi. He was awarded *Padma Bhushan* and so many honorable awards during his writing span of five decades. Several of his writings have become the great classics of Indian Theatre and Indian literature.

Tendulkar presents modern man in all his complexities. He portrays life from different angles. His plays concentrate on different aspects of human character. All of them underscore the complexities of human relationship. His plays make a subtle critique of modern middle-class and lower middle-class Indian society. The themes of gender discrimination, sexual norms, violence, and stability in the society, man-woman relationship, and institution of marriage, social issues, power and morality have been featured prominently in his plays. His plays have made an attempt to provide a comprehensive critical

statement on human relationships. The present plays, *Silence! The Court is in Session* and *Kamala* are also not exception.

About the Theme of Man- Woman Relationship:

Man- Woman relationship is the universal theme of the literature. The relation between a man and a woman never to be taken as relation between two equals. The roles of man and woman are basically different. Modern life has become more mechanical and more complex. This is affecting over all human relations. The Indian society is traditional and conventional. It is patriarchal and male dominated. The man has got supreme power over female. In Indian society woman is treated as a secondary object. The woman is not having independent existence. Her existence and living is for the sake of man. She has no identity. Whatever identity she is supposed to have is given to her by males. She is like a slave and male is like a master. She has to follow the duties prescribed by the man. The woman is treated like the property of the male. There are so many prejudices about the woman in the male dominated society. Beauvoir describes the bad condition of woman to man upon both the old and new testaments in *The Second Sex*: "For the man is not of the woman but the woman of the man. Neither was the man created for the woman but the woman for the man..... for the husband is

the head of wife even as Christ is the head of Church. Therefore, as the church is subject upto Christ, So let the wives are to their husband in everything.”(Beauvior, Simone de 1974:110) It shows that the man is not created for woman but the woman is created for man.

Marriage is a social institution. It is based on the traditions, customs and social morality. In the transitional period this relationship is also affected. Marriage is the most significant and socially recognized form of man-woman relationship.

Tendulkar has made a deep impact on contemporary Indian theatre. He has dealt with the issues of social injustice and the loneliness of the disillusioned individual that arises from his conflict with the hostile society. There is a realistic portrayal of the contemporary men and women in his plays centering on various social problems. He is intensely aware of what is going on in the world around him and faithfully reflects the strains and pressures of his milieu through his characters. Their virtues and weaknesses, joys and sorrows, love and hatreds are just like that of the ordinary human beings. G.P. Deshpande, a contemporary Marathi playwright and critic, observes that Tendulkar’s plays are notable for their uncompromising realism, merciless probing of human nature and candid scrutiny of individual and group psychology.

Tendulkar has created memorable male and female characters. The women characters in Tendulkar’s plays include housewives, teachers, mistresses, daughters, slaves and servants. Tendulkar exposes the pitiable condition of women in our society through these characters. Male characters are quite different from each other in behavioural traits, class, character and social position. They are bound by the common thread of their similar attitude of looking towards women as their property. They consider women as nothing more than the objects of satisfying

their various needs in life. Thus all the male protagonists in Tendulkar's plays appear as exploiters of women. However, the playwright points out the basic exploitative and oppressive nature of our society through the behaviour of his characters.

Man – Woman Relationship in *Silence! The court is in session:*

The play *Silence! The Court Is In Session* is an English translation of a play written in Marathi in the year 1967 by *Vijay Tendulkar*. The title of this play in Marathi is “*Shantata! Court Chalu Aahe!*” The play is translated in English by Priya Adarkar. The play is located in Indian context of 1950’s Thus, the play draws upon situations that would be typical of the lives of men and women in the newly independent Indian state, undergoing rapid changes as it sought to assimilate modern ideas and incorporate these while trying to break free of the stranglehold of older constricting patterns and thought processes.

The play is constructed in three acts. It is the play within play portraying a cross-section of middle class society. It mostly dwells on sensitive social issues; socio-psychological introspection on women, man-woman relationships changing in transitional society etc.

The complexity in the play in relationship arises due to love and sexual relationships. All the co-actors have ganged up against Miss Benare. Her private life is exposed and publicly dissected, revealing her illicit love affair with her uncle, Professor Damle and her behaviour with other co-actors. The beginning of Benare’s exploitation begins with her uncle who had exploited her sexually when she was only of fourteen. As he was uncle it was no question of getting married to him. She asserts this love in her monologue and says,

Miss Benare: I did commit a sin. I was in love with my mother’s brother..... he

praised my bloom...I insisted on marriage... And my brave man turned tail and ran. (Act Three p.74)

But the tragedy is that her uncle only had lust for her blooming body. She starts her life all over again, studies and becomes a teacher. As a teacher she comes in contact with Prof. Damle whom she considers quite intelligent and academically superior man. Though married, the professor exploits her sexually and naturally refuses to marry her. When she became pregnant from him, she began to search a father of unborn child for avoiding a social wrath and humiliation. It is Benare who is accused of immortality, sin, promiscuity, over sexuality. The verdict dismisses her from her school job, orders for abortion, and blackens Leela Benare's name. The mentality of the people never changes in such cases they go on taunting and cursing her. Her name is connected with the co-actors even with Balu Rokade.

In the play *Silence!* the husband-wife relationship is presented through the relationship between Mr. Kashikar and Mrs. Kashikar. Mr. Kashikar is always seen with his wife. The pair of this husband-wife is a super hypocrite, leading a false life that is devoid of any meaning. Tendulkar brings out the hollowness of their life so well. Mr. Kashikar buys flowers for wife. Mrs. Kashikar buys shirts for husband. They make a constant show of fondles in public. About this Karnik says,

Karnik: When I for one see such public formalities between husband and wife, I suspect something quite different in private. (Act One p. 12)

Their perpetual show of love becomes distasteful and repulsive. Mr. Kashikar does not let the wife speak at all. Whenever she tries to give an opinion her husband shuts her up again and again. When Mr Kashikar sees Mrs Kashikar coming front again and again he says,

Mr Kashikar: She can't get among few people without wanting to show off! Shows off all the time! (Act One p. 22)

...Can't shut up at home, can't shut up here! (Act Tow p. 28)

Tendulkar through this relationship has clearly pointed out the Indian marriage and family system, where men dominate the women in their domestic domain and not allow them to involve in any decision. Woman always get the second place in their family. She is scolded and rebuked for nothing.

Master-servant relationship may be seen through the relationship between Balu Rokade and Kashikars. They have adopted Balu for their own security to look after them and drive away the boredom of their domestic life. They toil him and make a slave of him. He becomes the whipping boy for the couple .Mrs. Kashikar always tries to dominate Balu. Even though Mrs Kashikar is a woman, she plays the role of master and threatens Balu.

The economic relationship also exists in the play. Miss Benare is working and earning money. Her earning makes her to stand on her own feet. She is independent and could live a free life as she wishes. But the traditional society does not allow her to earn, as it is against the Hindu religion. Mrs Kashikar always has to depend on her husband for survival. Miss Benare ridicules that. Her earning is also issue of discussion of the co-actors. They all want to dismiss her from the job so that she would be dependent.

The play also highlighting on social problems of Indian society, through this play tries to explore certain issues of contemporary society like middle class mentality and its pettiness. It exposes the dark side of middle class morality, where judgments are passed by the minute and silence is often the only recourse left to the defendant. This very reversal in the attitude of the

authorities expresses the basic hypocrisy and double standards on which our society is founded.

Man –Woman Relationship in *Kamala*:

In the play *Kamala* the husband-wife relationship is presented through the relationship between Jaysingh and Sarita. Jaysingh's attitude towards his wife is not much different as he uses her only as an object of enjoyment and as a slave to look after his house. He does not give any importance to the fact that Sarita's support and encouraging has helped him in building a successful career. Catherine Thankamma aptly comments that "Jaisingh remains totally indifferent to Sarita's feelings. He expects Sarita to submit to his desire for intercourse whether she wants it or not and calls her a 'bitch' when she refuses to cooperate with him". Through the character of Jaysingh, Tendulkar sheds light on the male egoism, domination, selfishness and hypocrisy of the modern success-oriented generation.

On the other hand Sarita is a modern Indian woman who is caught between the opposite pulls of tradition and modernity. Though Sarita is an educated urban lady, she is treated with scant respect by her husband, While Jaysingh remains absent from home for long periods, she looks after everything dutifully. She does everything that is possible to please Jaysingh. She is nothing else to her husband but only caretaker of the house. Her rebel is for the short time.

The relationship between Jaysingh and Kamala is the relation between the helpless woman and selfish journalist, the master and the slave. He buys her and wants to present her before public in the most miserable and abject condition so that he can win applause for rescuing such a sufferer. He just wants to use Kamala as a ladder to get money, reputation and fame. He has not any consideration what will happen to her after that. He is not really concerned about the

plight of helpless women. Shailaja Wadikar observers that, "Jaisingh uses Kamala as a means by which he can get a promotion in his job and win reputation in his professional career". However, she is just as use – and – throw object.

On the other hand Kamala has submitted herself to Jaysingh. She has no objection. She feels that it is the destiny of women like her. She accepts Jaysingh as her master whole-heartedly and is ready to do anything for him. She imagines that Jaysingh is going to keep her as his mistress. But Jaysingh sends her to an orphanage. Through Jaysingh's exploitation of Kamala, Tendulkar exposes the self-centeredness and insensibility of the modern careerist generation.

However, Tendulkar's depiction of male and female characters is realistic. Both the plays have very lucidly presented the existential man - woman relationship. It reflects the Indian mentality of that time boldly without any hesitation. They criticize the Indian society for its double standard living. Tendulkar has rightly picked up the theme of man - woman relationship and staged it and became the spokesman of the mankind.

References:

1. Tendulkar, Vijay. *Silence! The Court is in Session*. Oxford University Press, 1978.
2. Gokhale, Shanta. Tendulkar Priya, Mehta Kumud., Translated. *Five Plays: Kamala, Silence! The Court is in Session, Sakharam Binder, The Vultures, Encounter in Umbugland* by Vijay Tendulkar. Oxford University Press India 1996.
3. Kirdat, Pandurang A. "Human Relationships in Vijay Tendulkar's *Kamala: A Study*", *The Criterion*, An International Journal in English Vol.4 Issue II April 2013.
4. Beauvior, Simone de. *The Second Sex*. New York: Random House, 1974.

5. Deshpande, G.P. *Modern Indian Drama An anthology*. ed. G. P. Deshpande. Sahitya Academy. New Delhi. 2000. p. xviii.
6. Kundu, Tanmoy. “*Exploitation of Women in Vijay Tendulkar’s Plays Silence! The Court is in Session and Kamala*” www.galaxyimrj.com Galaxy: International Multidisciplinary Research journal, Vol. II., Issue. II, March 2013.
7. Chaugule, R. B. “*The Theme of Human Relationship in Vijay Tendulkar’s A Friend’s Story*”. THEMATICS, Vol. 1 Issue 1, Jan.2010.
8. Dharan, N.S. “*Vijay Tendulkar: A Unique Writer*” The Plays of Vijay Tendulkar (Creative new literature series), Creative Book Company, 1999.
9. Dharan, N.S. “*The Tongue – in cheek in Silence and Kamala*”. The Plays of Vijay Tendulkar (Creative new literature series), Creative Book Company, 1999.
10. Wadikar Shailaja B. *Vijay Tendulkar A Pioneer Playwright*. New Delhi: Atlantic Publishers & Distributors (P) Ltd. 2008. p. 24.
11. Thankamma, Catherine. Women that Patriarchy Created: The Plays of Vijay Tendulkar, Mahesh Dattani and Mahasweta Devi. Madge V.M. *Vijay Tendulkar’s Plays An Anthology of Recent Criticism*. New Delhi: Pencraft International. 2007. p. 81.